

Preparation and Spectroscopic Studies of Charge Transfer Complexes of Indolyldiene Aniline Derivatives with Di- and Tri-nitrobenzenes

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The solid CT complexes of some indolyldiene aniline derivatives with di- and tri-nitrobenzenes have been prepared and investigated by ir, electronic and ^1H nmr (DMSO d_6) spectroscopy. Non-acidic or weakly acidic acceptors yield complexes having $\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$ bonding. Strong acidic acceptors yield complexes having $\pi-\pi^*$ and proton transfer interaction. The formation of 1 : 2 (D : A) complexes is also ascertained. The ionisation potential of the donors as well as the electron affinities of the acceptors are determined from the electronic absorption spectra.

CHARGE transfer complexes of the donor-acceptor type based on the derivatives of nitrobenzene as acceptors have been of interest to several authors¹⁻⁹. The aniline derivatives included in the previous investigations contained mainly one π -donor centre, hence only 1 : 1 complexes are formed. For Schiff bases of aniline with benzaldehydes derivatives, 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 (D : A) complexes are formed irrespective of the type of bonding in the molecular complexes^{3,4}.

The present communication reports the investigation of the interaction between indolyldiene aniline derivatives and some di- or tri-nitrobenzenes. It is aimed to verify whether the stoichiometry of the molecular complexes formed is 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 and to identify the types of bonding contributing to their formation. Also, the ionisation potentials of the donors and the electron affinities of the acceptors are evaluated from the energies of the CT bands in the electronic spectra.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of pure grade (B.D.H.) products. The donors used have the general formula

where, X is H (a), OCH_3 (b), OH (c) and NO_2 (d). The acceptors used were picric acid (I), 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (II), 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid (III), 3,4-dinitrobenzoic acid (IV), *m*-dinitrobenzene (V) and 2,4-dinitrophenol (VI). The complexes were prepared in ratios of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (D : A) using the

procedure described previously^{5,6}. Some selected 1 : 2 compounds were subjected to C, H and N determinations (Table 1).

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Unicam SP 1000 spectrophotometer electronic absorption

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF SOME 1 : 2 (D : A) CT COMPLEXES

Acceptor no.	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd)		
		O	H	N
Complexes of indolyl-phenylazomethine				
I	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{14}$	49.40 (47.77)	3.70 (2.51)	11.00 (10.92)
III	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{13}$	52.50 (54.01)	3.80 (2.90)	13.90 (13.04)
VI	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{10}$	54.50 (55.70)	3.60 (3.20)	14.90 (14.30)
Complexes of indolyl- <i>p</i> -hydroxyphenylazomethine				
I	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{15}$	46.80 (46.70)	3.00 (2.60)	11.90 (10.08)
III	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{13}$	50.50 (52.70)	3.00 (3.08)	12.20 (12.70)
V	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_9$	55.50 (56.60)	3.00 (3.50)	14.60 (14.70)
Complexes of indolyl- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenylazomethine				
II	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{11}$	49.60 (50.96)	4.10 (3.40)	12.00 (11.89)
III	$\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{11}$	52.90 (53.39)	3.80 (3.90)	12.40 (12.50)
V	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_6\text{O}_9$	55.90 (57.30)	4.40 (3.80)	14.30 (14.32)
VI	$\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{11}$	54.80 (54.30)	4.80 (3.60)	13.20 (13.60)
Complexes of indolyl- <i>p</i> -nitrophenylazomethine				
II	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_7\text{O}_{12}$	46.20 (48.20)	4.20 (2.60)	12.80 (13.50)
IV	$\text{C}_{29}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_7\text{O}_{14}$	47.40 (50.50)	3.20 (2.80)	15.80 (14.20)

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TABLE 2—IR BANDS (cm⁻¹) FOR SOME OT COMPLEXES OF DONORS a, b, c AND d WITH STRONG ACIDIC ACCEPTORS*

D	D/A	M.p. °C	Colour	ν_{NH}	ν_{OH}	$\nu_{\text{asym. NO}_2}$	$\nu_{\text{sym. NO}_2}$	ν_{CHAr}
Complexes with picric acid								
Free acceptor					3 110	1 555, 1 540, 1 530	1 330	784
a	1 : 1	193	Deep orange	2 500, 2 950		1 595, 1 575, 1 525	1 335, 1 370	710, 745, 790
	1 : 2	159	Yellowish brown	2 500, 2 950	3 100	1 590, 1 565	1 335, 1 370	710, 745
b	1 : 1	176	Pale brown	2 600, 2 900		1 590, 1 570	1 330, 1 360	710, 780, 790
	1 : 2	151	Yellowish brown	2 600, 2 900	3 110	1 590, 1 570, 1 510	1 335, 1 365, 1 390	710, 735, 750, 775
c	1 : 1	126	Deep green	2 800, 2 900		1 565, 1 550	1 335, 1 360	710, 750, 790
	1 : 2	139	Deep green	2 800, 2 900	3 100	1 540, 1 570	1 350, 1 390	710, 745, 790
d	1 : 1	180	Brown	2 500, 2 900		1 590, 1 570, 1 530	1 320, 1 340, 1 370	710, 750, 790
	1 : 2	136	Deep brown	2 500, 2 900	3 100	1 590, 1 570, 1 530	1 330, 1 360	710, 740, 790
Complexes with 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid								
Free acceptor				3 560	3 560	1 540, 1 530	1 349	915, 925
b	1 : 1	220	Pale brown	2 500, 2 960	3 200	1 600, 1 510	1 320, 1 340	940
	1 : 2	206	Deep yellow	2 500, 2 960	3 300	1 590, 1 505	1 320, 1 340	940
c	1 : 1	190	Black	2 600, 2 800	3 200	1 600, 1 570, 1 510	1 335, 1 350	940
d	1 : 1	116	Deep orange	2 500, 2 900	3 500	1 600, 1 535	1 335, 1 380	940
	1 : 2	161	Deep orange	2 500, 2 900	3 500, 3 100	1 540, 1 575, 1 600	1 320, 1 350	935
Complexes with 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid								
Free acceptor					3 090	1 555, 1 540	1 350	923, 808
a	1 : 1	156	Orange	2 800, 2 900		1 535, 1 580, 1 595	1 340, 1 380	880, 920
	1 : 2	162	Orange	2 800, 2 900	3 100	1 540, 1 590	1 340	910, 920
b	1 : 1	161	Yellow	2 700, 2 900		1 580, 1 540	1 340, 1 380	830, 890, 900, 925
	1 : 2	179	Orange	2 700, 2 900	3 100	1 540, 1 580, 1 510	1 340	835, 910, 925
c	1 : 1	200	Black	2 500, 2 900		1 580, 1 540	1 350	840, 925
	1 : 2	141	Black	2 500, 2 900	3 100	1 550, 1 580	1 340, 1 380	840, 920
d	1 : 1	141	Brown	2 600, 2 950		1 580, 1 540	1 345, 1 390	840, 910, 920
	1 : 2	106	Pale brown	2 600, 2 950	3 100	1 545, 1 580, 1 600	1 335, 1 345	810, 840, 920
Complexes with 3,4-dinitrobenzoic acid								
Free acceptor					3 100	1 550	1 350, 1 325	930, 925
d	1 : 1	134	brick	2 600, 2 900		1 550, 1 600	1 395, 1 370, 1 330	920
	1 : 2	121	brown	2 600, 2 900	3 100	1 550, 1 600	1 320, 1 350, 1 370	920

*D=donor, A=acceptor, asym.=asymmetric, sym.=symmetric, Ar=Aryl

spectra (nujol) on a Shimadzu UV 250 spectrophotometer, and ¹H nmr spectra on a Varain EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer in DMSO-d₆ (Merck) using TMS as an internal standard.

Results and Discussion

Infrared spectra :

Charge transfer complexes from weak acidic and non-acidic acceptors : This class of complexes are formed using acceptors V and VI. The ir spectra of the compounds display some interesting changes as compared to those of their free constituents. The ν_{CH} bands of the acceptors display a shift to lower wavenumbers whereas those of the donors show an opposite shift (Table 2) which is characteristic of charge-transfer of the $\pi-\pi^*$ type^{7,8}. For 1 : 1 complexes, the ν_{CH} bands of the anilino ring display a higher shift denoting that this ring is the origin of charge donation to the acceptor. The shift of the indolyl bands is due to the resonance between the two rings involving charge migration from this ring to the anilino one under the influence of the positive hole left on the donor anilino ring. For the 1 : 2 complexes, the ν_{CH} bands of both the rings display almost comparable shifts.

The shifts for the 1 : 2 complexes are of higher magnitude since the donor molecule is subjected to the influence of two acceptor ones.

The ν_{NO_2} bands of the acceptor molecules display some interesting behaviour. The asym. NO₂ bands display a shift to lower wavenumbers which is in accordance with the increased π -electron density on the ring of the acceptor molecule. Also, the sym. NO₂ bands show a shift to lower wavenumbers, hence $n-\pi^*$ interaction is to be excluded^{7,9}. The magnitude of the shift is generally higher in the 1 : 1 complexes as compared to the 1 : 2 complexes since the resonance between the two Schiff base rings is inhibited in the 1 : 2 complexes. The interaction of the two aromatic rings with *m*-dinitrobenzene in the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes can be represented as

Charge transfer complexes of strong acidic acceptors : These complexes are formed when the donors are allowed to react with the acceptors I-IV. The ir spectra of these complexes are characterised by a group of new broad bands at 2 400-3 000 cm⁻¹ which are not present in the spectra of the free donors or acceptors (Table 2). These bands are assigned to the stretching vibration of a hydrogen attached to a quaternary positive nitrogen ion

(-HN⁺=C) which is formed through the transfer of a proton from the acidic centre of the acceptor to the nitrogen of the donor. This assumption is based on the disappearance of the bands due to protons of the phenolic OH group of acceptors I and II and carboxylic group of acceptors III and IV.

The -HN⁺=C bands have much higher intensity in the 1 : 2 complexes. The ν_{CH} bands of the acceptors shifted to lower values whereas those of the donors shifted to the higher ones. These bands display same behaviour as those in CT complexes involving electron transfer only. In the 1 : 1 compounds, the asym. and sym. NO₂ bands shift to lower values compared to those of the free acceptor as a result of increased polarisation of the NO₂ groups. Thus, the complexes of this class are formed through π-π* bonding as well as proton transfer. Hence, the CT complexes formed are formulated as

Electronic absorption spectra :

The electronic absorption spectra of the CT complexes formed with acceptors V and VI are characterised by only one CT band within the wavelength range 340-410 nm. The band observed is assigned to the π-π* CT interaction, which is substantiated by calculating the energy of the CT interaction (E_{CT}) using the relation of Briegleb¹⁰,

$$E_{CT} = I_p - (E_A - C)$$

where, E_{CT} is the energy of the CT interaction (π-π*) and I_p the ionisation potential of donors. The values of I_p are determined from the electronic absorption spectra using the relation,

$$I_p = a + b\nu_0$$

where, ν₀ is the energy of the HOMO-LOMO π-π* transition, a and b are constants having values³ 4.39 and 0.857 (Ref. 11) or 5.156 and 0.778 (Ref. 12) or 5.11 and 0.701 (Ref. 13). The mean values obtained are given in Table 4. Assuming that E_A=0.3 eV¹⁸ for acceptor-V, the mean value of C was found equal to 4.48 eV. Thus the electron affinity of the different acceptors used in the present investigation can be evaluated from E_{CT} values since the values of I_p and C are known (Table 4). The energy values determined from the CT bands, using the relation E_{CT}=1243.667/λ_{CT}, amount to 3.66-3.03 eV (Table 4). The CT complexes formed with strong acidic acceptors I-IV exhibit one or two CT bands in the 350-490 nm range. The bands are observed at higher energies compared to the case of the CT complexes not involving the proton transfer. The blocking of the lone-pair of the azomethine nitrogen through proton transfer indicates that n-π* interaction has a low contribution to the bonding in the CT complexes or even absent. The CT bands of the 1 : 2 complexes are observed at

TABLE 3—IR BANDS FOR SOME CT COMPLEXES OF DONORS a, b, c AND d WITH SOME WEAK NONACIDIC* ACCEPTORS

D	D/A	M.p. °C	Colour	ν _{OH}	ν _{asym.NO₂}	ν _{sym.NO₂}	ν _{CHAr}
Complexes with 2,4-dinitrophenol							
Free acceptor				3 270	1 540, 1 520	1 350	825, 928
a	1 : 1	99	Pale yellow		1 530, 1 570	1 330, 1 375	830, 925, 880
	1 : 2	121	Deep yellow	3 360	1 520, 1 560, 1 600	1 330, 1 375	840, 910, 925
b	1 : 1	181	Yellow		1 535, 1 560	1 330, 1 350, 1 380	830, 880, 920
	1 : 2	171	Deep yellow	3 120, 3 340	1 530, 1 570, 1 600	1 330, 1 350, 1 380	830, 850, 880, 920
c	1 : 2	144	Deep yellow	3 300, 3 400	1 540, 1 460	1 340, 1 350	840, 850, 920, 930
d	1 : 1	102	Brown		1 540, 1 500	1 330, 1 345	840, 920
	1 : 2	79	Deep yellow	3 200, 3 400	1 540, 1 560	1 340, 1 390	840, 920
Complexes with m-dinitrobenzene							
Free acceptor					1 545	1 352	920, 905
a	1 : 1	86	Pale brown		1 540, 1 580, 1 600	1 350, 1 370	905, 970
	1 : 2	66	Pale yellow		1 535, 1 580, 1 590	1 345, 1 390	910, 970
b	1 : 1	79	Pale brown		1 580, 1 550	1 350	915, 940, 960, 970
	1 : 2	69	Pale brown		1 540, 1 580	1 350	910, 960, 970
c	1 : 1	88	Black		1 580, 1 580	1 345, 1 395	910, 950, 970
	1 : 2	121	Black		1 535, 1 590	1 345, 1 395	910, 970
d	1 : 1	99	Orange		1 540, 1 595	1 350, 1 370, 1 390	910, 960
	1 : 2	71	Orange		1 540, 1 580	1 345	910

*Explanation of symbols as in Table 2.

TABLE 4—EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF E_{CT} FOR SOME COMPLEXES*

Acceptor no.	E_A	Ratio	^a ($I_P=7.98027$)		^b ($I_P=7.8491$)		^c ($I_P=7.8042$)		^d ($I_P=7.4989$)	
			λ_{CT}	E_{CT}	λ_{CT}	E_{CT}	λ_{CT}	E_{CT}	λ_{CT}	E_{CT}
I	0.69	1 : 1	—	—	375	3.32	360	3.45	375	3.30
		1 : 2	400	3.11	420	2.96	—	—	430	2.89
II	0.72	1 : 1	—	—	380	3.27	450	2.76	—	—
		1 : 2	360	3.27	430	2.89	350	3.55	—	—
III	0.50	1 : 1	—	—	390	3.19	450	2.76	380	3.27
		1 : 2	—	—	490	2.50	400	3.11	380	3.27
IV	0.75	1 : 1	—	—	390	3.19	—	—	—	—
		1 : 2	—	—	380	3.27	—	—	—	—
V	0.30	1 : 1	—	—	—	—	340	3.66	410	3.03
		1 : 2	—	—	390	3.19	350	3.55	390	3.19
VI	0.74	1 : 1	—	—	390	3.19	—	—	400	3.11
		1 : 2	—	—	410	3.03	410	3.03	410	3.03

* λ (nm), E_{CT} (eV).

 TABLE 5—¹H NMR SPECTRA FOR SOME CT COMPLEXES OF DONORS a, b AND d WITH SOME ACCEPTORS

Ratio & position	Signal of acceptor part						Signal of donor part								
	H ^a	H ^b	H ^c	H ^d	H ^e	OH	H ^a	H ^b ,H ^c	H ^d H ^e	H ^f	H ^a ,H ^b	H ^c ,H ^d	=NH	⁺ =NH	=OH
Complexes of indolyl-3-phenylazomethine															
Complexes with picric acid															
free A or D	—	8.46	—	8.46	—	6.16	7.20	7.45	7.60	8.50	8.00	8.50	—	8.70	7.55
1 : 1	—	8.35	—	8.35	—	—	8.70	7.75	7.85	8.90	8.30	8.90	3.80	9.55	7.50
1 : 2	—	8.30	—	8.15	—	10.00	7.40	7.75	7.80	8.65	8.20	8.65	4.80	9.60	7.50
Complexes with 3,5-dinitrobenzoic acid															
free A	8.80	—	9.03	—	8.80	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
1 : 1	8.35	—	9.00	—	8.50	—	7.35	7.65	6.80	8.80	8.20	8.80	4.65	10.00	6.65
1 : 2	8.25	—	8.90	—	8.20	—	8.80	7.30	6.70	9.10	9.00	9.10	4.3	10.60	6.60
Complexes with <i>m</i> -dinitrobenzene															
free A	9.00	—	8.43	—	8.43	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
1 : 1	8.80	—	8.95	—	8.25	—	7.30	7.85	8.60	8.85	8.20	8.85	—	10.00	7.40
1 : 2	8.85	—	8.20	—	8.00	—	7.35	7.90	8.45	8.75	8.10	8.75	—	10.00	7.25
Complexes with 2,4-dinitrophenol															
free A	—	9.20	—	8.50	7.30	10.80	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
1 : 1	—	9.00	—	8.35	7.20	—	7.50	8.20	8.40	8.65	8.25	8.65	3.70	10.00	7.00
1 : 2	—	8.70	—	8.20	7.10	7.20	7.50	7.30	6.80	8.70	8.20	8.70	4.6	9.10	6.90
Complexes with indolyl-3-(<i>p</i> -methoxyphenylazomethine)															
Complexes with 2,4-dinitrophenol															
free D	—	—	—	—	—	—	7.60	7.20	7.35	8.90	8.50	8.10	—	8.90	7.00
1 : 1	—	8.80	—	8.40	7.30	—	7.60	7.20	7.50	9.70	8.80	8.20	3.80	10.00	7.10
1 : 2	—	9.10	—	8.40	7.20	10.60	7.65	7.15	7.40	3.75	8.80	8.25	3.50	10.20	7.30
Complexes with indolyl-3-(<i>p</i> -nitrophenylazomethine)															
Complexes with 2,4-dinitrophenol															
free D	—	—	—	—	—	—	7.70	6.80	7.40	—	8.20	8.40	—	10.45	8.75
1 : 1	—	8.80	—	8.50	7.30	—	8.00	6.80	7.40	—	8.10	8.45	4.50	10.00	6.05
1 : 2	—	8.90	—	8.40	7.00	7.60	7.80	6.90	7.50	—	8.30	8.60	4.70	10.30	6.70

higher energy compared to those of the 1 : 1 type as a result of the blocking of the resonance between the two rings in the former type of compounds.

The plots of E_{CT} as a function of I_p of the donors^a exhibit satisfactory linear relationships with approximately identical slopes but varied intercepts indicate the validity of the Briegleb relation¹⁰ to the systems under study. The electron affinities of the acceptors under investigation are determined

from the intercepts. The values obtained graphically are in good agreement with those calculated from the Briegleb equation¹⁰.

¹H nmr spectra :

¹H nmr spectra of the CT complexes, when compared to those of the free components, reveal that the signals of the donor are shifted downfield whereas those of the acceptors shifted to the higher

ones. This is due to the $\pi-\pi^*$ interaction leading to the decrease of π -electron density on the donor and increase on the acceptors.

The spectra of the CT complexes of acceptors I-IV exhibit a new broad signal at δ 3.7-4.8 corresponding to the protons of $\text{CH}=\overset{+}{\text{N}}\text{H}$ centre. This is supported by the disappearance of the signal in the phenolic group of acceptors I and II or in the carboxylic group of acceptors III and IV.

For the 1 : 2 (D : A) complexes, the OH signals of the acceptors are observed. The magnitude of the shift of the donor signals (Table 5) is higher for 1 : 2 than for 1 : 1 CT complexes since the donor molecule is subjected to the influence of two acceptors. As for the signals of the acceptors, the shifts are lower for the 1 : 2 complexes since the donating molecule is distributed between two acceptor centres while in the 1 : 1 complex the donation is concentrated on one acceptor molecule only.

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